

POHINONAW TO BOTOSANON (TEACHING OF CULTURE): PRESERVING, PROMOTING, AND SUSTAINING OF OBO – MONUVU INDIGENOUS CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Abstract

The first – year implementation of B.A. Calamba National High School as a regionally certified Indigenous People Education (IPED) implementing school has yielded remarkable results and discussions centered around a comprehensive set of school-based interventions aimed at preserving, promoting, and sustaining the cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu indigenous community. This paper summarizes the outcomes and insights derived from these interventions, which have significantly contributed to strengthening the implementation of IPED and fulfilling the school's roles and responsibilities as an IPED implementing institution in preserving, promoting, and sustaining the cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu indigenous community. The school-initiated interventions encompass a range of activities and strategies: *Nonawwan* (Indigenous Learning Space), *Kod Nonaw woy Kotuwihan* (Teaching and Learning Sessions), Social Media Campaign, Curriculum Integration, Capacity Building and SLAC Session, *Od Tawwan to Pusaka* (Obo – Monuvu Museum), and Obo – Monuvu Library Hub. These comprehensive efforts benefit not only the Obo – Monuvu community but also provide valuable insights for educational institutions seeking to support indigenous cultural heritage preservation. The multifaceted approach has enriched both teachers and students, fostering a deeper connection to and appreciation for the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people.

Keywords: *cultural heritage, intervention, indigenous people, preservation, preservation, sustainability*

INTRODUCTION

The preservation of indigenous cultural heritage is essential for students to understand, respect, and appreciate the diversity of indigenous cultures. However, several challenges and issues may make it difficult for educational settings to effectively preserve the indigenous cultural heritage. These issues include the limited inclusion of indigenous history and culture in formal education curricula, the disappearance of indigenous languages making it difficult to transmit traditional knowledge and cultural practices, lack of indigenous educators in educational institutions, scarcity of culturally appropriate educational materials, and cultural disconnect leading to an identity crisis (King & Schielmann, 2004).

Similar challenges arise in B.A. Calamba National High School such as limited integration of indigenous heritage in the classroom instruction, gradual language loss among younger generations of indigenous students, insufficient number of educators able to transmit indigenous knowledge and traditions, lack of teaching materials that are culturally appropriate, and cultural disconnection, especially indigenous students living outside their traditional communities.

Like many indigenous communities, the Obo – Monuvu face challenges in preserving, promoting, and sustaining their cultural heritage in the face of globalization, modernization, and marginalization. The Obo – Monuvu people are an indigenous group residing in Mindanao, Philippines. They have a rich cultural heritage that encompasses unique traditions, beliefs, languages, arts, and practices. The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2015) describes culture as a powerful driver for development that has community-wide social, economic, and environmental impacts. Likewise, UNESCO identified two ways to preserve cultural heritage: one is to document it in tangible form and save it in an archive, and the other is to maintain it in a living form by ensuring that it is passed on to future generations. These efforts will lead to preservation, promotion, and sustainability of indigenous cultures and traditions (Williams et. al., 2019).

In response to the persistent challenges in the Obo – Monuvu community, the B.A. Calamba National High School which caters OboMonuvu students conducted the *Pohinonaw to Botosanon* (Teaching of Culture) Program which encompasses school-initiated interventions to help preserve, promote, and sustain the Obo – Monuvu indigenous cultural heritage.

The Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines mandates non-formal, informal, and indigenous learning systems as well as selflearning, independent, and out-of-school youth study programs, particularly those that respond to community needs. In response to this, the Department of Education through the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (R.A. 10533) adopted a learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally appropriate, and culturally sensitive curriculum. Likewise, the DepEd Order No. 62, s. 2011, also known as Adopting the National Indigenous Peoples (IP) Education Policy Framework highlights the provision of adequate and culturally appropriate learning resources and environment to IP learners which is a key step to achieving the country's commitment to Education for All (EFA).

Anent to this, the Region Memorandum CLMD No. 153 s. 2021, otherwise known as Establishment of Cultural Heritage Learning Centers (CHLC) in schools implementing

IPED program in SOCCSKSARGEN region mandates provision of support in the development of culturally appropriate learning environment context of the Indigenous Peoples' (IP) learners. The establishment of the CHLC aims to transmit indigenous knowledge and skills to IP learners in the public schools within the Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs), maximize the presence of IP elders or culture bearers from the community as resource persons for the skills transfer, increase the number of IP learners who practice and master the indigenous skills, and encourage ICCs to maintain the practice of these indigenous knowledge and skills.

The B.A. Calamba National High School recognized its crucial role for fostering cultural identity among students, preserving cultural diversity, promoting inclusivity, and sustaining indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu. With this, the school conducted various interventions to help preserve, promote, and sustain the Obo – Monuvu cultural heritage which are as follows:

Nonawwan (Indigenous Learning Space)

The school designated one classroom to be the Nonawwan aside from the corner for each classroom for students not only on the Obo – Monuvu tribe can enjoy different learning materials. The designated classroom is also open to all teachers for them to bring their students to have their classes on it.

Kod Nonaw woy Kotuwihan (Teaching and Learning Sessions)

Through the help of the Cultural Masters or Tribal Elders, the students were given the chance to learn directly from the experts through different learning sessions.

Kod Nonaw to Uwahingon (Teaching of Obo – Monuvu Songs)

A Cultural Master that is an expert in Obo – Monuvu songs taught students on the different songs accompanied by the instruments.

Kod Nonaw to Binovallan (Teaching of Musical Instruments)

This session focused on teaching students how to play the different instruments that are heritage to the culture of Obo – Monuvu. These instruments are as follows:

- I. *Kod Nonaw to Lantuy* (Teaching of Lantuy)
- II. *Kod Nonaw to Kuglung* (Teaching of Kuglung)
- III. *Kod Nonaw to Sowroy* (Teaching of Sowroy)

Kod Nonaw to'd Ilutù (Teaching how to cook)

In this session different techniques unique in the Obo – Monuvu tribe were taught to students.

- I. *Linutlut no Binggala* (Cooking of root crops)
- II. *Linutlut no Kannon* (Cooking of steamed rice)

Od Tawwan to Pusaka (Obo – Monuvu Museum)

The school on its Nonawwan designated a place to showcase the different artifacts of Obo – Monuvu donated by the different stakeholders who are a proud member of the tribe. Among the artefacts displayed are the musical instruments, garments, and the like.

Obo – Monuvu Library Hub

This school – initiated intervention seeks to help students access the different learning materials prepared by the teachers during the SLAC sessions and stories written by the Cultural Masters and Tribal Elders.

Social Media Campaign

Social media as a powerful tool for promoting the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu were also utilized by the school as an intervention to reach a wider audience and to have a visual tour and exhibits on the richness of the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu.

Curriculum Integration

Curriculum integration is a powerful tool for promoting, preserving, and sustaining the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo - Monuvu people. Indigenous cultures often face the risk of erosion and loss due to various factors, including globalization, urbanization, and the dominance of mainstream educational systems.

Capacity Building and SLAC Sessions

Capacity building and SLAC (Seminars, Workshops, Learning Activities, and Conferences) sessions are essential components of efforts to promote, preserve, and sustain the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people. These initiatives help empower the community, enhance their knowledge and skills, and strengthen their ability to safeguard their cultural heritage.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main purpose of the study was to investigate the impacts of *Pohinonaw to Botosanon* (Teaching of Culture) program in preserving, promoting, and sustaining the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu in B.A. Calamba National High School. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the school-initiated interventions to preserve, promote, and sustain the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu in B.A. Calamba National High School?
2. How do these school-initiated interventions preserve, promote, and sustain the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu in B.A. Calamba National High School?
3. What are the impacts of these school-initiated interventions on the teachers and students of B.A. Calamba National High School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative research through ethnographic participant observation and interaction to comprehensively investigate the preservation, promotion, and sustainability of the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu. The ethnographic research design is appropriate in the study because it involves the systematic investigation of the Obo – Monuvu people and their culture and entails immersive fieldwork, participant observation, and in-depth interviews to gain a deep understanding of their culture.

Participants of the Study

Participants of the study were the students, teachers, school administrator, Obo – Monuvu Cultural Masters and Bearers, and Tribal Elders.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in B.A. Calamba National High School, Pangao-an, Magpet, Cotabato.

Data Collection

In – depth interviews, focus group discussions, and document analysis were conducted to explore the school-initiated interventions, their mechanisms, and their perceived impacts. These sessions were audiorecorded and transcribed for analysis. Field and observation notes were also done to further support and validate the responses of the participants. Data collected, especially Obo – Monuvu terms were validated and checked by the Cultural Masters and Tribal Leaders before it was analyzed to ensure the validity and reliability of the transcribed data.

Data Analysis

The researchers took on interpretive research paradigm, wherein it gave emphasis on the sociocultural lens that focuses on the investigation and interpretation of meaning in a social interaction (Lin, 2015).

The analysis of the data of the study was confronted both by the answers during the interview and field notes during the conduct of the schoolinitiated interventions and the reflections and insights of teachers during the SLAC session. Narrative research analysis was employed in making sense of the data gathered. Teachers localized lesson plans and SLAC reflections were analyzed through integrative review as Torracco (2005) stated, analyzes and synthesizes the available resources, which in this study lesson plans and reflection, to create new frameworks or views on the preservation, promotion, and sustainability of cultural heritage.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, the importance of ethical consideration was emphasized. The researcher preserved the participants' rights under RA 10173, often known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The information obtained were kept highly confidential and used only for legal purposes and lawful processing. As a result, the researcher cautiously followed the procedures and standards in order to adhere to the ethical considerations in the conduct of this study.

Respect for Autonomy. All participants signed first an informed consent before participating in the study after explaining to them using the language they understand the nature and goal of the study. They had the right to withdraw from participating in the study anytime they wish.

Justice. The participants of the study were not discriminated, exploited, and harmed at any point of the study.

Nonmaleficence. To protect the anonymity of the research participants, a coding scheme for each participant was employed during the analysis to ensure the confidentiality of their identities.

Beneficence. Even though there was no direct financial gain to the participants of the study, the platform of which the research offers in preserving, promoting, and sustaining the indigenous cultural heritage of Obo – Monuvu was more valuable than the former.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The B.A. Calamba National High School, as a regionally certified Indigenous People Education (IPED) implementing school, conducted various school-based interventions to help strengthen the implementation of the IPED and fulfill its roles and responsibilities in preserving, promoting, and sustaining Obo – Monuvu cultural heritage.

School-Initiated Interventions

Nonawwan (Indigenous Learning Space)

In accordance with the definition of cultural sustainability, material culture consists of practices, techniques, and processes that are curated constantly by human capital (Brown et. al., 2022). In this study, *Nonawwan* served as a learning space where cultural masters and tribal leaders shared their years of experience through the *kod nonaw woy kotuwihan* (teaching and learning sessions) where the Obo – Monuvu students immersed themselves in the *kod nonaw to uwahingon* (teaching of Obo – Monuvu songs), *kod nonaw to binovallan* (teaching of musical instruments) like *lantuy*, *kuglung*, and *sowroy*, and *kod nonaw to'd ilutù* (teaching how to cook) *binggala (kamoteng kahoy)* and *kannon*

(steamed rice). These activities enabled the transfer of indigenous skills and knowledge and the preservation of the Obo – Monuvu cultural heritage as students developed a stronger appreciation for their heritage and become more aware of the need to protect it.

Figure 1

Figure 2 *Nonawwan (Indigenous Learning Space)*

Students Utilizing the Nonawwan (Indigenous Learning Space)

Kod Nonaw way Kotuwihan (Teaching and Learning Sessions)

The teaching and learning sessions were done through the help of Cultural Masters or Tribal Elders. They were assigned on different sessions based on their expertise. The school had invited a total of 12 cultural masters and tribal leaders to help facilitate the teaching and learning sessions.

Figure 3

Schedule of Podnonaw way Kotuwihan (Teaching and Learning Sessions)

B.A. CALAMBA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL			
SESSION SCHEDULE			
DATE	TIME	RESOURCE PERSONS/CULTURAL MASTERS	GRADE LEVEL
Feb. 1, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Feb. 15, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Feb. 22, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Mar. 1, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Mar. 8, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Obat O. Bacag, Boi Fe Bacag	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Mar. 15, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Obat O. Bacag, Boi Fe Bacag	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Mar. 22, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Galuyan Bantac, Boi Elizabeth Bacag	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Mar. 29, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Galuyan Bantac, Boi Elizabeth Bacag	Grade- 7
	9:00-10:00		Grade-8
	10:15-11:15		Grade-9
Apr. 5, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
Apr. 12, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
Apr. 19, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
Apr. 26, 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Olimpio Empoc, Datu Mamerto Empoc	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
May 3 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Obat O. Bacag, Boi Fe Bacag	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
May 10 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Obat O. Bacag, Boi Fe Bacag	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
May 17 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Galuyan Bantac, Boi Elizabeth Bacag	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12
May 24 2023	8:00-9:00	Datu Ronelo Empoc, Boi Elizabeth Bacag	Grade-10
	9:00-10:00		Grade-11
	10:15-11:15		Grade-12

There were several teaching and learning sessions held in the *Nonawwan*.

A. Kod Nonaw to Uwahingon (Teaching of Obo – Monuvu Songs)

B. Kod Nonaw to Binovollan (Teaching of Musical Instruments)
Figure 5

Different Obo – Monuvu Musical Instruments

b.1 Kod Nonaw to Lantuy (Teaching of Lanty)

b.2 Kod Nonaw to Kuglung (Teaching of Kuglung)

b.3 Kod Nonaw to Sowroy (Teaching of Sowroy)

C. *Kod Nonaw to'd Ilutù* (Teaching how to cook)

c.1 *Linutlut no Binggala*

c.2 *Linutlut no Kannon*

Od Tawwan to Pusaka (Obo – Monuvu Museum)

A school museum dedicated to the Obo – Monuvu's indigenous cultural heritage served as an educational cornerstone for promoting and preserving their rich traditions. Through immersive experiences, it enhanced cultural education and awareness, imparting a profound understanding of Obo – Monuvu history and practices. The museum also safeguarded valuable artifacts and crafts, preventing their loss and decay while contributing to language and oral tradition preservation.

Figure 11

Od Tawwanto Pusaka Obo– Monuvu Museum)

These artifacts were donated by the different who are proud members of the Obo – Monuvu tribe as a proof of their strong and commitment to promoting, and sustaining their rich cultural heritage. It became a catalyst for cultural revival, sparking renewed interest in rituals and ceremonies while encouraging community with interactive exhibits, it fostered engagement and cross-cultural understanding, making the learning process captivating and inclusive. Moreover, the museum's role in documentation ensured that cultural knowledge was meticulously preserved, and its promotion of art and crafts empowered cultural pride and economic sustainability. Class activities within the museum further enriched students' cultural understanding, including traditional art forms and practices. Ultimately, this institution acted as a repository for endangered cultural practices, fortifying Obo – Monuvu's heritage and promoting a sense of cultural ownership and pride among its students and community.

Obo – Monuvu Library Hub

A library hub dedicated to the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu is a vital institution for promoting, preserving, and sustaining their culture. It acts as a repository for valuable cultural materials, including documents, artifacts, and recordings, ensuring their protection for future generations. This resource provides a platform for cultural education, enabling both community members and the wider public to gain insights into Obo – Monuvu history, language, traditions, and practices. Additionally, the library supports language preservation, research, and academic scholarship, inspiring a renewed interest in Obo – Monuvu cultural practices and serving as a catalyst for cultural revival. It fosters intercommunity exchanges, empowers the community to actively participate in cultural preservation, provides legal and intellectual property support, hosts cultural celebrations, facilitates cross-generational learning, promotes cross-cultural understanding, and acts as an advocacy hub. In essence, the library empowers the Obo – Monuvu community to preserve and promote their cultural heritage, ensuring its vibrancy and relevance for generations to come.

Figure 12

Obo – Monuvu Library Hub

Figure 13

Literatures Displayed in the Obo – Monuvu Learning Hub

Social Media Campaign

In pursuit of reaching wider audience, the school with the help of the school’s media team showcased the school-initiated interventions and activities to the DepEd Dose sa Ere (DDE) and awarded as Outstanding Maka-tao Episode of the Year 3rd Placer and Outstanding Male Reporter in the person of Randy P. Osorno. Social media posts on Facebook through the school’s official Facebook page DepEd Tayo B.A. Calamba NHS were also done to further promote the cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu.

Figure 14
Social Media Campaign

Curriculum Integration

Curriculum integration is a powerful tool for promoting, preserving, and sustaining the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people. Indigenous cultures often face the risk of erosion and loss due to various factors, including globalization, urbanization, and the dominance of mainstream educational systems. Curriculum integration, in this context, refers to the incorporation of indigenous knowledge, values, traditions, and languages into the formal education system.

Classroom instruction is essential for promoting, preserving, and sustaining the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people. It played a pivotal role in passing down traditional knowledge, values, languages, and practices to younger generations. This educational approach fostered cultural awareness, pride, and identity while ensuring the preservation of indigenous languages and traditional knowledge. Classroom instruction through the involvement of the community and elders, also promoted respect for ancestral traditions, taught cultural art and crafts, emphasized environmental stewardship, enhanced cross-cultural understanding, educated students about legal and human rights, aided in cultural revitalization, and prepared students for cultural celebrations. It was a powerful tool for preserving and revitalizing the rich cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people for future generations. Contextualize lesson plans through integrating Obo – Monuvu practices were done. The integration of indigenous knowledge was also evident in the contextualized lesson plans.

Figure 16

Capacity Building and SLAC Sessions

REFLECTION

The results presented in the context of B.A. Calamba National High School's first-year implementation as a regionally-certified Indigenous People Education (IPED) implementing school are promising and demonstrated a concerted effort to promote, preserve, and sustain the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu. Several school-initiated interventions have been implemented to achieve these objectives, and the findings shed light on the significance of these efforts.

The establishment of the Indigenous Learning Space (*Nonawwan*) is commendable as it allows for the transfer of indigenous skills and knowledge from Cultural Masters and Tribal Elders to younger generations. This hands-on approach aligned with the principles of cultural sustainability, ensuring that practices, techniques, and processes are curated and passed down. The involvement of recognized experts from the Obo – Monuvu community further authenticated the knowledge being imparted.

The Teaching and Learning Sessions (*Kod Nonaw woy Kotuwihan*) facilitated by Cultural Masters and Tribal Elders were crucial in promoting cultural education. The diversity of sessions, including teaching Obo – Monuvu songs, musical instruments, and traditional cooking methods, highlights the multifaceted nature of the cultural heritage. These sessions contributed to the preservation of language, traditional art forms, and practices, and fostering a deeper connection to Obo – Monuvu culture among students.

The Social Media Campaign and Curriculum Integration efforts were strategic in reaching a wider audience and embedding Obo – Monuvu cultural elements into the school's educational framework. Leveraging digital platforms and integrating cultural practices into lesson plans enhanced cultural visibility and understanding.

The Capacity Building and SLAC Sessions played a pivotal role in empowering the Obo – Monuvu community. These initiatives facilitated knowledge transfer, cultural education, and environmental stewardship while also promoting cross-cultural understanding and advocacy for indigenous rights. The emphasis on legal and human rights awareness is particularly important in safeguarding cultural heritage.

The establishment of a school museum is a significant milestone in preserving Obo – Monuvu's cultural heritage. The museum not only served as an educational resource but also acted as a tangible representation of the community's commitment to preserving its rich traditions. It provided a space for cultural artifacts and crafts, preventing their loss and decay while promoting language and oral tradition preservation. The interactive nature of the museum ensures that learning about Obo – Monuvu culture is engaging and memorable for students and visitors. Furthermore, the museum's role in documenting and archiving cultural knowledge ensures that it is preserved meticulously for future generations.

The Obo – Monuvu Library Hub is another crucial resource, serving as a repository for cultural materials and supporting cultural education. It empowered community members and the wider public to access valuable insights into Obo – Monuvu history, language, and traditions. The library hub's support for language preservation and academic research fostered a deeper understanding of Obo – Monuvu culture. Its role as a hub for cultural exchange, community engagement, and advocacy is pivotal in promoting cross-cultural understanding and safeguarding cultural heritage.

In summary, the results highlight a multi-faceted approach undertaken by B.A. Calamba National High School to preserve, promote, and sustain the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu. These initiatives encompassed education, documentation, intergenerational learning, community empowerment, advocacy, and cultural celebrations. The comprehensive efforts not only benefitted the Obo – Monuvu community but also contributed to a broader understanding of indigenous cultural heritage preservation. It is evident that the school's commitment to these endeavors is making a meaningful impact, and the lessons learned can serve as a valuable model for other educational institutions seeking to support indigenous cultural heritage. The concept of intercultural education goes beyond the recognition of the existence of more than one culture in a society and promotes cross-cultural understanding and the integration of different languages and systems of learning and teaching.

The school-initiated interventions implemented by B.A. Calamba National High School have had significant impacts on both teachers and students, fostering a deeper connection to and appreciation for the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu people.

Impact to Teachers and Students

Nonawwan (Indigenous Learning Space). The establishment of the *Nonawwan* as an Indigenous Learning Space has provided teachers and students with a unique opportunity to interact with Cultural Masters and Tribal Elders. This hands-on learning approach has allowed them to immerse themselves in the indigenous skills and knowledge of the Obo – Monuvu, creating a direct connection to their cultural heritage.

Teachers have also benefitted from these sessions, gaining a deeper understanding of Obo – Monuvu practices that they can incorporate into their teaching.

Kod Nonaw woy Kotuwihan (Teaching and Learning Sessions). The teaching and learning sessions conducted by Cultural Masters and Tribal Elders had a profound impact on both teachers and students. These sessions have not only preserved and promoted Obo – Monuvu cultural practices but have also served as a source of inspiration for teachers and students alike. Teachers have learned how to integrate Obo – Monuvu cultural elements into their curriculum, making their instruction more culturally sensitive and engaging. Students had the opportunity to learn directly from experts, fostering a sense of pride in their cultural heritage and a desire to learn more.

Social Media Campaign. The school's efforts to display its initiatives through social media have not only reached a wider audience but have also instilled a sense of pride and accomplishment among teachers and students. Winning awards for Outstanding Maka-tao Episode and Outstanding Male Reporter has undoubtedly boosted the morale of the school media team and the entire school community. It has demonstrated the power of their efforts in promoting and preserving Obo-Monuvu culture, encouraging continued dedication.

Curriculum Integration. The integration of Obo – Monuvu practices into the curriculum has transformed the educational experience for both teachers and students. Teachers modified their lesson plans to incorporate indigenous knowledge, values, traditions, and languages, deepening their own understanding of Obo – Monuvu culture. Students, on the other hand, learned about their own cultural heritage within the formal education system, fostering cultural awareness, pride, and identity.

Capacity Building and SLAC Sessions. These sessions have not only enhanced the knowledge and skills of teachers but have also empowered them to actively participate in cultural preservation efforts. Teachers have become advocates for Obo – Monuvu cultural heritage, raising awareness and promoting cross-cultural understanding within the school and the wider community. Students have benefited from the enriched curriculum and the cross-generational learning facilitated by these sessions.

Od Tawwan to Pusaka (Obo – Monuvu Museum). The school museum has provided both teachers and students with a tangible representation of Obo – Monuvu cultural heritage. It has served as an educational cornerstone, enhancing cultural education and awareness. Teachers have used the museum as a resource for teaching, and students have had the opportunity to engage with interactive exhibits, making their learning experience captivating and memorable.

Obo – Monuvu Library Hub. The library hub dedicated to the indigenous cultural heritage of the Obo – Monuvu has become a valuable resource for teachers and students. It has provided access to cultural materials and supported cultural education. Teachers have used the library to enrich their teaching, and students have gained insights into Obo – Monuvu history, language, traditions, and practices.

In other words, the school-initiated interventions contributed to cultural preservation and heritage protection, educational enrichment through the integration of indigenous knowledge to teaching practices and contextualization of learning, promoted indigenous language and arts, strengthening cultural identity and inclusivity, cultural documentation and language revitalization, social justice and equity, community involvement and partnership, and empowering the Obo – Monuvu students.

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